

Table S3: Gene pathway analysis of RNA-seq studies comparing Ala92-Dio and Thr92-Dio2 iBAT.

Gene set	Description	Enrichment score	P-value	FDR step up	Rich factor	Genes in set
path:mmu03040	Spliceosome	26.33	3.69E-12	1.26E-09	9.92E-01	133
path:mmu04140	Autophagy - animal	24.32	2.73E-11	4.69E-09	9.85E-01	137
path:mmu04141	Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum	22.39	1.90E-10	2.17E-08	9.69E-01	161
path:mmu05012	Parkinson disease	19.40	3.76E-09	2.97E-07	9.36E-01	233
path:mmu00190	Oxidative phosphorylation	19.26	4.33E-09	2.97E-07	9.82E-01	113
path:mmu04714	Thermogenesis	17.94	1.62E-08	9.28E-07	9.38E-01	208
path:mmu04932	Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease	14.28	6.27E-07	2.82E-05	9.45E-01	145
path:mmu05415	Diabetic cardiomyopathy	14.23	6.58E-07	2.82E-05	9.30E-01	185
path:mmu01100	Metabolic pathways	13.98	8.52E-07	3.25E-05	8.46E-01	1359
path:mmu05208	Chemical carcinogenesis - reactive oxygen species	13.81	1.01E-06	3.45E-05	9.22E-01	205
path:mmu03010	Ribosome	13.60	1.24E-06	3.87E-05	9.43E-01	141
path:mmu04144	Endocytosis	12.92	2.44E-06	6.98E-05	9.06E-01	256
path:mmu05010	Alzheimer disease	12.78	2.82E-06	7.43E-05	8.94E-01	329
path:mmu05014	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	12.49	3.75E-06	9.20E-05	8.94E-01	320
path:mmu04120	Ubiquitin mediated proteolysis	12.40	4.11E-06	9.40E-05	9.37E-01	142
path:mmu04137	Mitophagy - animal	12.08	5.67E-06	1.22E-04	9.85E-01	67
path:mmu05020	Prion disease	11.22	1.34E-05	2.71E-04	9.03E-01	236
path:mmu03013	Nucleocytoplasmic transport	10.32	3.31E-05	6.30E-04	9.43E-01	105
path:mmu00970	Aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis	10.03	4.40E-05	7.95E-04	1.00E+00	45
path:mmu05016	Huntington disease	9.95	4.79E-05	8.21E-04	8.90E-01	272
path:mmu04142	Lysosome	9.70	6.12E-05	9.99E-04	9.28E-01	125
path:mmu05132	Salmonella infection	9.61	6.69E-05	1.04E-03	8.93E-01	243
path:mmu04910	Insulin signaling pathway	9.46	7.76E-05	1.16E-03	9.24E-01	131
path:mmu04152	AMPK signaling pathway	9.24	9.69E-05	1.38E-03	9.26E-01	122
path:mmu05222	Small cell lung cancer	9.18	1.03E-04	1.42E-03	9.44E-01	90
path:mmu04150	mTOR signaling pathway	8.79	1.53E-04	2.01E-03	9.15E-01	141
path:mmu03022	Basal transcription factors	8.69	1.68E-04	2.14E-03	1.00E+00	39
path:mmu05220	Chronic myeloid leukemia	8.56	1.92E-04	2.35E-03	9.49E-01	78
path:mmu03018	RNA degradation	8.38	2.29E-04	2.71E-03	9.48E-01	77
path:mmu00510	N-Glycan biosynthesis	8.34	2.39E-04	2.73E-03	9.80E-01	49
path:mmu05161	Hepatitis B	8.09	3.07E-04	3.40E-03	9.09E-01	143
path:mmu03020	RNA polymerase	8.02	3.29E-04	3.49E-03	1.00E+00	36
path:mmu04146	Peroxisome	8.00	3.36E-04	3.49E-03	9.40E-01	83
path:mmu04210	Apoptosis	7.42	6.02E-04	6.07E-03	9.08E-01	131
path:mmu03008	Ribosome biogenesis in eukaryotes	7.34	6.50E-04	6.33E-03	9.37E-01	79
path:mmu01200	Carbon metabolism	7.32	6.64E-04	6.33E-03	9.17E-01	109

path:mmu03015	mRNA surveillance pathway	7.13	8.04E-04	7.45E-03	9.25E-01	93
path:mmu04130	SNARE interactions in vesicular transport	6.90	1.01E-03	8.85E-03	1.00E+00	31
path:mmu04136	Autophagy - other	6.90	1.01E-03	8.85E-03	1.00E+00	31
path:mmu04919	Thyroid hormone signaling pathway	6.88	1.03E-03	8.86E-03	9.08E-01	120
path:mmu04213	Longevity regulating pathway - multiple species	6.53	1.46E-03	1.22E-02	9.48E-01	58
path:mmu04330	Notch signaling pathway	6.36	1.73E-03	1.40E-02	9.47E-01	57
path:mmu04722	Neurotrophin signaling pathway	6.35	1.76E-03	1.40E-02	9.05E-01	116
path:mmu04216	Ferroptosis	6.11	2.22E-03	1.73E-02	9.74E-01	38
path:mmu00520	Amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism	6.09	2.27E-03	1.73E-02	9.57E-01	47
path:mmu04211	Longevity regulating pathway	5.94	2.62E-03	1.96E-02	9.18E-01	85
path:mmu03050	Proteasome	5.90	2.73E-03	1.99E-02	9.57E-01	46
path:mmu01250	Biosynthesis of nucleotide sugars	5.71	3.30E-03	2.36E-02	9.72E-01	36
path:mmu05212	Pancreatic cancer	5.69	3.39E-03	2.36E-02	9.21E-01	76
path:mmu04066	HIF-1 signaling pathway	5.67	3.44E-03	2.36E-02	9.04E-01	104
path:mmu05211	Renal cell carcinoma	5.59	3.72E-03	2.50E-02	9.26E-01	68
path:mmu01522	Endocrine resistance	5.51	4.05E-03	2.67E-02	9.10E-01	89
path:mmu05022	Pathways of neurodegeneration - multiple diseases	5.37	4.67E-03	3.00E-02	8.50E-01	408
path:mmu03420	Nucleotide excision repair	5.36	4.72E-03	3.00E-02	9.53E-01	43
path:mmu00900	Terpenoid backbone biosynthesis	5.12	5.99E-03	3.74E-02	1.00E+00	23
path:mmu04931	Insulin resistance	5.08	6.22E-03	3.81E-02	8.96E-01	106
path:mmu04070	Phosphatidylinositol signaling system	4.87	7.67E-03	4.62E-02	9.01E-01	91
path:mmu05210	Colorectal cancer	4.84	7.91E-03	4.68E-02	9.05E-01	84
path:mmu04068	FoxO signaling pathway	4.79	8.29E-03	4.82E-02	8.86E-01	123
path:mmu00640	Propanoate metabolism	4.73	8.81E-03	5.03E-02	9.68E-01	31
path:mmu00310	Lysine degradation	4.69	9.19E-03	5.15E-02	9.19E-01	62
path:mmu00562	Inositol phosphate metabolism	4.68	9.31E-03	5.15E-02	9.13E-01	69
path:mmu00630	Glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism	4.54	1.07E-02	5.73E-02	9.67E-01	30
path:mmu00020	Citrate cycle (TCA cycle)	4.54	1.07E-02	5.73E-02	9.67E-01	30
path:mmu05160	Hepatitis C	4.51	1.10E-02	5.79E-02	8.80E-01	133
path:mmu05171	Coronavirus disease - COVID-19	4.37	1.27E-02	6.59E-02	8.62E-01	210
path:mmu05417	Lipid and atherosclerosis	4.34	1.30E-02	6.65E-02	8.66E-01	186
path:mmu05223	Non-small cell lung cancer	4.28	1.38E-02	6.95E-02	9.04E-01	73
path:mmu05213	Endometrial cancer	4.25	1.42E-02	7.06E-02	9.15E-01	59

path:mmu05017	Spinocerebellar ataxia	4.20	1.50E-02	7.28E-02	8.77E-01	130
path:mmu01521	EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor resistance	4.20	1.51E-02	7.28E-02	8.99E-01	79
path:mmu03060	Protein export	4.15	1.57E-02	7.49E-02	9.64E-01	28
path:mmu04012	ErbB signaling pathway	4.07	1.71E-02	8.03E-02	8.97E-01	78
path:mmu05200	Pathways in cancer	4.02	1.79E-02	8.24E-02	8.38E-01	476
path:mmu05205	Proteoglycans in cancer	4.00	1.82E-02	8.24E-02	8.62E-01	188
path:mmu00450	Selenocompound metabolism	4.00	1.83E-02	8.24E-02	1.00E+00	18
path:mmu00280	Valine, leucine and isoleucine degradation	3.97	1.88E-02	8.38E-02	9.20E-01	50
path:mmu03030	DNA replication	3.94	1.94E-02	8.51E-02	9.43E-01	35
path:mmu04510	Focal adhesion	3.85	2.13E-02	9.24E-02	8.59E-01	192
path:mmu05167	Kaposi sarcoma-associated herpesvirus infection	3.83	2.18E-02	9.34E-02	8.61E-01	180
path:mmu00563	Glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI)-anchor biosynthesis	3.77	2.30E-02	9.66E-02	9.62E-01	26
path:mmu05230	Central carbon metabolism in cancer	3.77	2.31E-02	9.66E-02	8.99E-01	69
path:mmu05206	MicroRNAs in cancer	3.54	2.89E-02	1.20E-01	8.62E-01	159
path:mmu05169	Epstein-Barr virus infection	3.49	3.06E-02	1.24E-01	8.54E-01	199
path:mmu05163	Human cytomegalovirus infection	3.47	3.11E-02	1.24E-01	8.52E-01	216
path:mmu04922	Glucagon signaling pathway	3.47	3.11E-02	1.24E-01	8.80E-01	92
path:mmu00500	Starch and sucrose metabolism	3.39	3.35E-02	1.31E-01	9.58E-01	24
path:mmu05221	Acute myeloid leukemia	3.39	3.36E-02	1.31E-01	8.94E-01	66
path:mmu05215	Prostate cancer	3.35	3.52E-02	1.36E-01	8.76E-01	97
path:mmu04935	Growth hormone synthesis, secretion and action	3.34	3.56E-02	1.36E-01	8.74E-01	103
path:mmu00513	Various types of N-glycan biosynthesis	3.24	3.93E-02	1.48E-01	9.21E-01	38
path:mmu05165	Human papillomavirus infection	3.21	4.05E-02	1.51E-01	8.40E-01	313
path:mmu04622	RIG-I-like receptor signaling pathway	3.15	4.29E-02	1.57E-01	9.02E-01	51
path:mmu04071	Sphingolipid signaling pathway	3.14	4.31E-02	1.57E-01	8.66E-01	119
path:mmu00051	Fructose and mannose metabolism	3.09	4.57E-02	1.65E-01	9.19E-01	37
path:mmu03430	Mismatch repair	3.02	4.86E-02	1.74E-01	9.55E-01	22
path:mmu01240	Biosynthesis of cofactors	2.99	5.04E-02	1.78E-01	8.60E-01	129

Genes in list	Genes not in list	Genes in list, not in set	Genes not in list, not in set	Gene set	Description
132	1	4964	1266	path:mmu03040	Spliceosome
135	2	4961	1265	path:mmu04140	Autophagy - animal
156	5	4940	1262	path:mmu04141	Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum
218	15	4878	1252	path:mmu05012	Parkinson disease
111	2	4985	1265	path:mmu00190	Oxidative phosphorylation
195	13	4901	1254	path:mmu04714	Thermogenesis
137	8	4959	1259	path:mmu04932	Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease
172	13	4924	1254	path:mmu05415	Diabetic cardiomyopathy
1150	209	3946	1058	path:mmu01100	Metabolic pathways
189	16	4907	1251	path:mmu05208	Chemical carcinogenesis - reactive oxygen species
133	8	4963	1259	path:mmu03010	Ribosome
232	24	4864	1243	path:mmu04144	Endocytosis
294	35	4802	1232	path:mmu05010	Alzheimer disease
286	34	4810	1233	path:mmu05014	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
133	9	4963	1258	path:mmu04120	Ubiquitin mediated proteolysis
66	1	5030	1266	path:mmu04137	Mitophagy - animal
213	23	4883	1244	path:mmu05020	Prion disease
99	6	4997	1261	path:mmu03013	Nucleocytoplasmic transport
45	0	5051	1267	path:mmu00970	Aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis
242	30	4854	1237	path:mmu05016	Huntington disease
116	9	4980	1258	path:mmu04142	Lysosome
217	26	4879	1241	path:mmu05132	Salmonella infection
121	10	4975	1257	path:mmu04910	Insulin signaling pathway
113	9	4983	1258	path:mmu04152	AMPK signaling pathway
85	5	5011	1262	path:mmu05222	Small cell lung cancer
129	12	4967	1255	path:mmu04150	mTOR signaling pathway
39	0	5057	1267	path:mmu03022	Basal transcription factors
74	4	5022	1263	path:mmu05220	Chronic myeloid leukemia
73	4	5023	1263	path:mmu03018	RNA degradation
48	1	5048	1266	path:mmu00510	N-Glycan biosynthesis
130	13	4966	1254	path:mmu05161	Hepatitis B
36	0	5060	1267	path:mmu03020	RNA polymerase
78	5	5018	1262	path:mmu04146	Peroxisome
119	12	4977	1255	path:mmu04210	Apoptosis
74	5	5022	1262	path:mmu03008	Ribosome biogenesis in eukaryotes
100	9	4996	1258	path:mmu01200	Carbon metabolism

86	7	5010	1260 path:mmu03015	mRNA surveillance pathway
31	0	5065	1267 path:mmu04130	SNARE interactions in vesicular transport
31	0	5065	1267 path:mmu04136	Autophagy - other
109	11	4987	1256 path:mmu04919	Thyroid hormone signaling pathway
55	3	5041	1264 path:mmu04213	Longevity regulating pathway - multiple species
54	3	5042	1264 path:mmu04330	Notch signaling pathway
105	11	4991	1256 path:mmu04722	Neurotrophin signaling pathway
37	1	5059	1266 path:mmu04216	Ferroptosis
45	2	5051	1265 path:mmu00520	Amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism
78	7	5018	1260 path:mmu04211	Longevity regulating pathway
44	2	5052	1265 path:mmu03050	Proteasome
35	1	5061	1266 path:mmu01250	Biosynthesis of nucleotide sugars
70	6	5026	1261 path:mmu05212	Pancreatic cancer
94	10	5002	1257 path:mmu04066	HIF-1 signaling pathway
63	5	5033	1262 path:mmu05211	Renal cell carcinoma
81	8	5015	1259 path:mmu01522	Endocrine resistance
347	61	4749	1206 path:mmu05022	Pathways of neurodegeneration - multiple diseases
41	2	5055	1265 path:mmu03420	Nucleotide excision repair
23	0	5073	1267 path:mmu00900	Terpenoid backbone biosynthesis
95	11	5001	1256 path:mmu04931	Insulin resistance
82	9	5014	1258 path:mmu04070	Phosphatidylinositol signaling system
76	8	5020	1259 path:mmu05210	Colorectal cancer
109	14	4987	1253 path:mmu04068	FoxO signaling pathway
30	1	5066	1266 path:mmu00640	Propanoate metabolism
57	5	5039	1262 path:mmu00310	Lysine degradation
63	6	5033	1261 path:mmu00562	Inositol phosphate metabolism
29	1	5067	1266 path:mmu00630	Glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism
29	1	5067	1266 path:mmu00020	Citrate cycle (TCA cycle)
117	16	4979	1251 path:mmu05160	Hepatitis C
181	29	4915	1238 path:mmu05171	Coronavirus disease - COVID-19
161	25	4935	1242 path:mmu05417	Lipid and atherosclerosis
66	7	5030	1260 path:mmu05223	Non-small cell lung cancer
54	5	5042	1262 path:mmu05213	Endometrial cancer

114	16	4982	1251 path:mmu05017	Spinocerebellar ataxia EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor
71	8	5025	1259 path:mmu01521	resistance
27	1	5069	1266 path:mmu03060	Protein export
70	8	5026	1259 path:mmu04012	ErbB signaling pathway
399	77	4697	1190 path:mmu05200	Pathways in cancer
162	26	4934	1241 path:mmu05205	Proteoglycans in cancer
18	0	5078	1267 path:mmu00450	Selenocompound metabolism Valine, leucine and isoleucine
46	4	5050	1263 path:mmu00280	degradation
33	2	5063	1265 path:mmu03030	DNA replication
165	27	4931	1240 path:mmu04510	Focal adhesion Kaposi sarcoma-associated herpesvirus
155	25	4941	1242 path:mmu05167	infection Glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI)-
25	1	5071	1266 path:mmu00563	anchor biosynthesis
62	7	5034	1260 path:mmu05230	Central carbon metabolism in cancer
137	22	4959	1245 path:mmu05206	MicroRNAs in cancer
170	29	4926	1238 path:mmu05169	Epstein-Barr virus infection
184	32	4912	1235 path:mmu05163	Human cytomegalovirus infection
81	11	5015	1256 path:mmu04922	Glucagon signaling pathway
23	1	5073	1266 path:mmu00500	Starch and sucrose metabolism
59	7	5037	1260 path:mmu05221	Acute myeloid leukemia
85	12	5011	1255 path:mmu05215	Prostate cancer Growth hormone synthesis, secretion
90	13	5006	1254 path:mmu04935	and action
35	3	5061	1264 path:mmu00513	Various types of N-glycan biosynthesis
263	50	4833	1217 path:mmu05165	Human papillomavirus infection
46	5	5050	1262 path:mmu04622	RIG-I-like receptor signaling pathway
103	16	4993	1251 path:mmu04071	Sphingolipid signaling pathway
34	3	5062	1264 path:mmu00051	Fructose and mannose metabolism
21	1	5075	1266 path:mmu03430	Mismatch repair
111	18	4985	1249 path:mmu01240	Biosynthesis of cofactors